

DELINQUENT BEHAVIOR AMONG ADOLESCENTS: MODERATING ROLE OF PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT AND FAMILY FUNCTIONING

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ABSTRACT

The present study was examining the relationship of Parental Involvement, Family Functioning predicting and moderating role of delinquent behavior among adolescents. Self-Report Delinquency Scale (naqvi, 2005), Intimacy Conflict Parenting Style (ICPS; Noller, Smith & Robert, 1992), individually administered to check parental involvement, family environment develop delinquency among adolescents. To mount up the relationship in above mentioned variables the Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used. Multiple Regressions was applied to check prediction. Male adolescents than female adolescents (with low socio-economic status) are more prone towards delinquency Results revealed that there was a strong relationship among delinquent behavior, family environment, and parental involvement. Furthermore findings suggested that healthy and positive bond with family; parents will become less delinquent behavior shows among adolescents (Juliana, 2000).

KEYWORDS: *Delinquency, Family Functioning, Delinquent Behavior, Parental Involvement.*

INTRODUCTION

Current study explores delinquent behavior among adolescents with the perspective of family environment (family functioning), and parental behaviour considered as social predictors of delinquency, dependent and independent variables were positively correlated (Amnah & Mustafa 2000). This research investigated the relationship of family life styles predicting delinquent behavior among adolescents. Individuals with the characteristics linked with the production of delinquent behavior. Individual causes like age and gender related disturbances, prenatal related complexities like birth time period showed in early childhood, on the other hands might not be happen until late childhood or in adolescence. Studies regarding criminal behavior continuously search out that the rates of offending begin at the stage of preadolescence (early adolescence) reach a peak in adolescence and throughout the young adulthood (Farrington 1986a, National Research Council, 1986).

DELINQUENT BEHAVIOR AMONG ADOLESCENT

Break rulers act on adolescence is closely universal in American children; many of these behaviors are mild and temporary, crimes remarkably consistent in different countries, boys with delinquent behavior from the age of 10 to 17, by the maximum level is in the age of twenty eight years old, self-report, offenders with the same sample from the ages of 15 and 18, then dropped on the age of 24. Longitudinal researches of boys of city Pittsburgh, the percentage of boys who told that their delinquent behavior rise from 5 percent to 6 to 18 percent for whites and 27 percent for blacks between the age of 16 (Lobber, 1998). The anti-social behavior and the consequences of the bad material related unhealthy offense act by adolescents, is due to the society setup and their norms for rich people separately and society setup and norms for poor, differently. It causes to develop delinquency anti-social behavior. Society should see and set the norms for adolescents to bring and nourish the healthy one and prevent and pretend from disorders which come from society (Bisera, 2002).

PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT

Relationship between the parents and its importance and then the delinquent behavior can be examined by the comfort and discomfort zone of child of his or her daily routine activities than the actual tracking behavior by the parents (Stettin & Kerr, 2000), observation by limited parenting, and adolescents spend less time with their parents and they are not controlled (Hirsch, 1969). un healthy negative bond of children with their parents at risk of setting a child

become delinquent which begin in initial time period teens, various delinquent actions consistently followed into adulthood (Moffitt, 1993; Patterson & Yoerger, 2002).

In adolescents one's who has an optimistic relationship with their fathers are less likely to be arrest or to belong to a gang and involve in irrational as compare to their peer one's with poor and less positive relationships to their fathers, with the increase of family poverty and risk of delinquency linked with the absence of their interlinked to other social problems. In 1990,s report the Department of Justice; those children came from authoritarian parenting become rebellious, abusive and more aggressive (Rehman, 1998).

FAMILY ENVIRONMENT

National Longitudinal data collection of health of adolescents (1995), the authors explain furthermore and investigate the effects of growing up in a two parent versus single parent family (single mother) delinquency in (single father) families too. This strategy help us to see the mechanisms through which live with single parent increase the delinquency, notably, and the effect is predominantly a function of parental absence parental gender. The results shows that adolescents in single parent families and neglectful parents having more delinquent than their counterparts residing with two biological, married parents, although these differences are reduce once the authors account it for many family processes. Moreover, family processes are the high level of delinquent behavior of adolescents from single-father versus single-mother families (Demuth & Brown, 2004).

Research included that critical measurements and analytic strategies has more intricate conceptualization of the relationship between family life like siblings and other family members and delinquency, all have important amplification for intervention with delinquents and their families. This review of research on the role of the family, it's based on family interventions with delinquent behaviors and the existing treatment outcomes and there search highlights four areas, the relationship between different family processes and delinquency the reciprocal relationships between parenting style and delinquent behavior, family affectedness the context on parenting and delinquency as one cause of delinquency among many (Carolyn & Susan, 1997).

SOCIAL THEORIES

BANDURA (1965) has demonstrated that aggressive behavior can be learned by reinforcement or imitation and modeling which come under social learning. Children and adolescents observed the behavioral patterns of their parents to each other, their peer sittings, cartoons all these major things bring a highlighted positivity or pessimism among them. Crime and violence which shown on televisions, at homes, among peers produce reinforcement to show any destructive or constructive behavior.

JULIAN ROTTER (1954-1982) contributes on social learning theories that behavior always occur and react in certain situation through learning imitation and observing. Behaviors produce through reinforcement, reinforcement might be positive or negative, when it will react as negative reinforcement it will automatically produce low self-esteem, and gradually it will lesser or higher with the passage of time and through experiments and learning.

DELINQUENT BEHAVIOR AMONG ADOLESCENTS: ROLE OF PARENTING STYLES AND FAMILY ENVIRONMENT

According to this research which was derived from Chinese culture and Chinese schools (Hong Kong) age from 14 to 19 and conceptualize that social theory social bonding theory labeling theory have effect on delinquency, low self-control is interlinked with delinquent in Chinese setting. Low self-control and many other factors (Peer Company, social setup, social interaction, stress full life events, and labialization from teachers and parents) cause delinquency and the delinquent behavior is also variate according to the culture of your social setup (Cheng & Chang, 2008). Juvenile delinquency is global problem now days; criminal behavior influenced by many major societal and psychological traits like poor and criminal peers, depressive, suppressive and neglected parenting and family atmosphere, unhealthy neighboring, uneducated or low educated social circle causes serious problems among children specially age from 12 to 18 years. Data was quantitatively analyzed. And check the delinquent's age, sex, family setup, family style, parent education, and heir socio economic status, and poor criminal peer pressure and then how low self-esteem easily noted down among delinquents. Results showed that there is highly positive correlation among all study variables; this study is applicable at Pakistani community (Kausar, Nadeem, Misbah & Fauzia, 2012).

OBJECTIVES

- To examine the relationship between Family Functioning and Parenting Styles predict delinquent behavior among adolescents.
- To identify the relationship of demographic variables among adolescents with delinquent behaviour.

HYPOTHESIS

H1. There would be a significant relationship of Family Environment and Family Functioning among adolescents with delinquent behavior.

- H2. Family environment would be positive predictor delinquent behavior among adolescents.
- H3. Parental involvement would be positive predictor of delinquent behavior among adolescents.
- H4. There would be gender differences in all the study variables.

METHODOLOGY

Study was consisted psychometrics properties of all scales were measured. In this study three translated scale was used; research design, sample, sampling techniques, instruments and procedure of data collection will be included.

RESEARCH DESIGN

In this study survey research design was used. Sample of this phase entailed adolescents (N= 700), collected from the Faisalabad division. The age range of the sample was 12 to 18 years.

SAMPLING STRATEGY

Convenient sampling technique was used to collect data.

INSTRUMENTS

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

It was used to assure that the data will be used only for the study purpose to obtain demographic information of the participation an appropriate demographic sheet was attached along with questionnaires. This information consists of gender, age, education, parent’s education, parent’s income.

SELF-REPORT DELINQUENCY SCALE

Scale developed by naqvi (2007) was used to differentiate between boys and girls having high SRD, five point linker scale with 27 items which are all positively stated .These are following dimensions, theft measured by (item no. 1,10,17,19)drug abuse measured by (2,8,9) lying measured by item no (20),noncompliance measured by item no(22),police encounter (14,25),violence (extroversion, vandalism, aggression) measured by item no(3,7,12,21,26,27) cheating and gambling (4,6,11,23,24), sex related (harassment, homosexuality, heterosexuality) measured by item no.(5,13,15,16,18).Scoring criteria is 0=never, once=1,2-4 times=2,5-10 times= 3,and 10 or more times=4.Cronbach’s Alpha was used for the self-report delinquency scale and find out .94.

INTIMACY CONFLICT PARENTING STYLES SCALE (ICPS)

ICPS originally develop by (noller, Seth smith, Mary, boumas, Ruth and Schweitzer Robert,1992) was used to assess the family functioning, 30 item scale and comprises of three sub scales intimacy ,conflict, parenting styles, items are arranged on a saw point likert scale response format arranging from 1=totally disagree to 6 = totally agree, subscale Intimacy items (1,4,6,10,13,15,18,20,23,26,27,29). Parenting Styles (2,7,11,16,21,25,28,30), 24 comprise the conflict factor. There is no reverse item. Alpha coefficients for the original sample were calculated at 0.92 for intimacy 0.68 for parenting style, and 0.82 for conflict.

PROCEDURE

First of all, principal and vice principal of private and Govt. schools and colleges of Faisalabad were personally contacted. After their permission, participants were approached in their class room. Instructions were given to participants about filling the scales. Furthermore, appropriate demographic sheet was attached at the top of each questionnaire to get necessary demographic information. The obtained data was then analyzed with the help of SPSS 20.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Main objective of the pilot study is to examine the psychometric properties of instruments that are proposed to use in the main study, to achieve this objective multiple statistical analysis were conducted including descriptive statistics, item total correlation, reliability analysis and skewness.

TABLE 1
Correlation Matrix for all the Variables Used in the Study (N = 700)

Variables	N	M	SD	Range	Potential	Actual	Skewness	1	2	3
1 DB	700	98.64	16.50	.71	5-135	.035		-	.57**	.59**
2 FF	700	85.80	7.56	.86	5-150	.289				-

Note. 1 = delinquent Behavior (DB); 2= family functioning (FF)

*p< .05, ** p < .01, ***p< .01

Table no 1 show the co relational analysis of the study variables used in the present study. The analysis reveals that the delinquency and family functioning is significant and positively correlated with delinquent behavior.

Table 4
Parental Involvement and Family Environment as a predictor of Delinquent Behaviour among adolescents (N= 700)

Variables	Theft			Drug Abuse			Lying			Non.Compliance			Police-encounter			Violence			Cheating/Gambling			Sex related		
	B	Δ R ²	F	B	Δ R ²	F	B	Δ R ²	F	B	Δ R ²	F	B	Δ R ²	F	B	Δ R ²	F	B	Δ R ²	F	β	Δ R ²	F
INT	.40 ***	.16	81.4**	.28 ***	.18	51.3**	.37 ***	.15	41.6**	.17 ***	.06	15.0**	.27 ***	.27	88.7**	.28 ***	.18	52.8**	.11 ***	.05	45.2**	.40 ***	.28	94.8**
PS	.20 ***			.16 ***			.35 *			.13 ***			.19 ***			.24 ***			.33 **			.19 ***		
CF	.08 *			.16 ***			-.25			.03 *			.28 ***			.07			.23 **			.15 ***		

Note. INT = Intimacy, PS = Parenting Style, CF= Conflict Factor.

*p < .05, **p < .01, ***p < .001

Multiple regression analysis processed to check the effect on constructs of delinquent behavior on Intimacy, Parenting style, Conflict, factor showed that 26% of the variance resulted by a model comprising constructs of delinquent behavior i.e. theft. The drug abuse described 18% variance. Lying explained 15% variance, noncompliance 6%, police encounter 27%, violence 18%, cheating/gambling 31% and sex related 28%. It Represent that the model indicate positively significant among the predictors.

Table 5

Comparison of Male and Female adolescents on family function delinquent behavior among adolescents (N = 700)

Variables	Male (n = 400)		Female (n = 300)		t(695)	P	95% CI		Cohen's D
	M	SD	M	SD			LL	UL	
D.B	65.39	39.45	60.57	11.92	18.93***	.000	18.03	1.85	1.62
FF	67.84	47.64	70.71	4.27	15.62**	.000	7.57	2.10	1.15

Note. D.B= Delinquent Behavior; FF = family functioning;

*p .05. **p < .01. ***p<.001.

Results demonstrate the mean gender differences and effect size on Delinquency and other scales. The mean difference is found to be significant on self. Delinquency appraisal {t (695) = 18.93, p< .05}, family functioning {t (695) = 15.62, p< .01}, whereas female adolescents found to be lower delinquent behavior, and effect more male adolescents rather than female adolescents.

Table 6

Comparison of Father Income between thirty thousand and below and more than thirty thousand on Psycho-Social predictors of Delinquent behaviour among adolescents (N = 700)

Variables	Thirty thousand and below (n=355)		More than thirty thousand (n=345)		t(695)	P	95% CI		Cohen's d
	M	SD	M	SD			LL	UL	
D.B	70.20	15.21	72.57	11.39	-7.26***	.000	4.24	1.85	.42
FF	74.90	6.24	110.20	19.92	-2.67***	.000	7.57	2.10	.32

Note. D.B= Delinquent Behavior; FF = family functioning;

*p .05. **p< .01. ***p<.001

Results in Table 15 demonstrate the mean Father’s income and effect size on Delinquency and other scales. The mean difference is found to be significant on self. Delinquency appraisal {t (695) = -7.26, p< .05}, family functioning {t (695) = -2.67, p< .001}, implies that low Father’s income below thirty thousand were higher on delinquent behavior.

CONCLUSION

In this research check the relationship of parental involvement, family functioning and peer pressure among adolescents with delinquent behavior. Role of gender, father income was also investigating. The goal of the study was fully supported that the social predictors i.e parental involvement, family processes predict delinquent behavior among adolescents. Most of the hypotheses in the study were showing the desired results. Present study also explored the gender differences as well as the role of socioeconomic status of delinquent behavior among adolescents. The findings

confirm that male adolescents significantly scored high on parental involvement, family functioning with delinquent behavior as compare to female adolescents.

DISCUSSION

Main study with 700 adolescents and some demographic variable (i.e., gender and father income) was also explored. Main study also examined the psychometric properties of all scales. The data was analyzed statically in term of mean, standard deviation, correlation, regression, t-test, one-way Anova, Cronbach's alpha reliability was applied. All hypothesis was supported in the study. In the present study seven major variables (including independent variable, dependent variable), studied to observe the effect of parental involvement, family environment, and then the tendency of these aspects shows delinquent behavior. Results of present study showed the significant correlations among all four study variables among adolescents with delinquent behavior. The correlations were directed in the desired direction (Mustufa, 1998). Erick Erickson the adolescent's age from 13 to 21, Identity vs. Role Confusion, it is the fifth stage of development, adolescent must struggle to discover his or her identity. And understand the social interactions, psychological interaction and how to fitting in, and to develop the sense of moral values, right from wrong. Those who aren't successfully reach on this stage, become having avoidant personalities and violent, confused personalities, as an output they act any criminal activity and show delinquent behavior at teen age or young adulthood called delinquency.

Reliability analysis was run to check the psychometric properties of the questionnaires which were found to be satisfactory. Correlation analysis was run to check the relationship pattern between main variables and their subscales. Multiple regression analysis was performed to check the impact of development of delinquent behavior due to parental involvement, peer pressure, family functioning. After reliability analysis this study addresses the frequency of demographic variables and percentages. The percentage of adolescent's age ranges from 12 to 18 years, greater than the female participants. Father's income was greater in percentage than the Mother's income (Ismat & Ali et al., 2001), it is also concluded that from the age of 13 years to 22 years old adolescents, cross sectional and parametric analysis was used in this research, gender difference and self-reported issued determined at this study . According to the results female adolescents had hidden confusions and limited behavioral reactions, female showed less behavioral issue (delinquency), at the same time they have psychological and social issues and there were a significant level observed during the research (Mckan et al., 1998), findings revealed that family functioning positively correlated with the delinquent behavior among adolescents. Multiple regression analysis between family environment and delinquent behavior among adolescents positively predict; unhealthy negative relationship and interpersonal conflicts with siblings, other family members increases and neglected, pessimist parenting cause the delinquent behavior among adolescents (Subtageen et al., 2004). Patterns of pleasant and unpleasant contacts were related to the development and set of family environment of adolescents. Negative family setup has damaging interpersonal relationships among siblings and other family members. Therefore it can be concluded that family environment is the core source of developing delinquent behavior among adolescents. National Longitudinal data collection regarding mental and physical health of adolescents (1995), the authors explain furthermore and investigate the effects of growing up in a two parent versus single parent family single mother delinquency in single father families too (Eden, 2017). Results showed that adolescents with single parent, broken families and neglectful parents having more adolescents with delinquent behavior than their counterparts residing with two biological, married parents, although these differences are reduce once the authors account it for many family processes. Moreover, non-serious, violent family processes face high level of delinquent behavior among adolescents (Brown, 2004).

Parental involvement consequences among adolescents. The study investigated the impact of parental involvement on adolescents' behavioral, social, and psychological issue. Mofit (1993) theorized that negative parental involvement increases high level of delinquent behavior among adolescents. Controlled or strict parenting, un healthy negative bond of children with their parents; at risk of setting a child become delinquent which begin in initial time period teens, various delinquent actions consistently followed into adulthood . According to Adrian there are strong evidences that parental intensely causes behavioral problems like anxiety depression and other behavioral and social problems .Strict, ignored and violent relationship of parents with their children positively significant with delinquent behavior and it would be stronger than the link between the week parental observations and the delinquent behavior. Children and parents are active stimuli in process of the link between knowledge on whereabouts of the child and delinquent behavior (Ahmad, 2009).

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